

The Nations with the Highest Borrowings Per Capita and Implications

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ABSTRACT

A nations' borrowing per capita can also be explained as debt to GDP ratio; this means that it's the country's dues compared to its economic yield, i.e., once the nations' economy slows down, the Government borrows to keep up its commitments and to rouse its economy. Both developed and developing countries borrow for investment projects that they cannot finance themselves, and most borrow from international credit markets based on their credibility to pay back the borrowed amount. In conclusion, this review has observed that Japan leads the nations among borrowing per capita at 236%, and Brunei is the lowest at two percent. The difference is that the poorer economies have to borrow in international currencies like the US dollar, and despite a good export of their products abroad, they still collect large external debts as compared to rich economies like the US. External debt is the main factor that destabilizes the capital flow into the country. The implications of a high debt by the Government in higher interest rates, inflation, and higher taxes have been briefly explained.

Keywords: Borrowing, Financial, Per capita

INTRODUCTION

A nations' borrowing per capita can also be explained as debt to GDP ratio; this means that it's the country's dues compared to its economic yield, i.e., once the nations' economy slows down, the Government borrows to keep up its commitments and to rouse its economy.

Furthermore, GDP is the country's total output of all its services and goods and per capita means per person, for example, the per capita GDP of the UK is 43 thousand dollars, and India is two thousand dollars. This measure calculates and compares the economic output of different countries (Focus economics, 2019).

The table given in Annexure 1 shows that Japan leads the nations among borrowing per capita at 236%, and Brunei is the lowest at two percent. This review is going to look into the various implications of this issue as to the reason for the differences between the nations' borrowing needs and capacities. For the sake of convenience of discussion, here a table is given of the top 10 countries with the highest Public Debt % of GDP

Table. 1: top 10 countries with the highest Public Debt % of GDP

Rank	Country	Public Debt % of GDP (projected)
1	Japan	236
2	Greece	175
3	Lebanon	153
4	Venezuela	152
5	Italy	131
6	Portugal	119
7	Singapore	116
8	Mozambique	114
9	United States	108
10	Belgium	100

(Source: Results from Focus Economics 2019)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Both developed and developing countries borrow for investment projects that they cannot finance themselves, and most borrow from international credit markets based on their credibility to pay back the borrowed amount.

Singer (1975) has explained his theory as borrowing per capita of the economy is linked to international trade. One school of thought is that international trade is vital to underdeveloped countries as it considerably affects their economy. Foreign trade is linked to the national income, i.e., is when the national income is at its lowest, the foreign trade proportionally higher. It is more fiercely pursued in under-developed countries as the trifling margins of income they gain over their sustenance are sources of capital development and thus see more export from such countries than their use of merchandise from abroad.

Olson (1996) has further expounded on this issue that some nations, for whatever reasons, are better off than the poorer nations and their per capita incomes are at least twenty times higher, and they do not necessarily share national borders. Most rich countries have robust economic policies and institutions to accomplish their potential. They have better legal, political and constitutional systems in place to protect the rights of their citizens. It has also been observed those transportation facilities, advanced technology to manufacture high-end goods like computers and airplanes, banking centers in London and Zurich; Japan, a great exporter of high quality manufactured products, has boosted their economy and increased their per capita income.

Holland (2007) has explained the reasons and implications of nations with the highest borrowings per capita because when a nation cannot borrow in its exchange, it collects external debt. The extent of the debt in foreign currency is the main determinant that affects the instability of the capital flows, stable output, and managing the foreign currency exchange rates and the country's credit ratings.

The developed economies, as a consequence, borrow mainly in foreign currency, and their investors have to reduce their portfolio diversification due to reducing marginal profits in adding risks and costs of each additional currency they have to deal in; as the trade, GDP, and domestic credit differ between different countries. The risk of a portfolio is amplified according to credit risk and transactions' cost due to the developing nation's currency. Larger economies have no wish to hold on to smaller economies' currency, but the smaller economies would like to hold on to higher foreign currency. The developing countries enter the international market late and have a huge task to add their currency to the international portfolio, and as they cannot borrow with their currency, they always suffer the consequences of financial mismatch. On the other hand, large economy dominated countries can deal in their currency but have little scope for diversification compared to the smaller economies with international transaction costs reap better benefits of diversification.

Most developing countries who borrow abroad have to deal with mostly the US dollar or Euro. The history of the US dollar has mostly been volatile, but its appreciation has increased even if its debt has escalated. This can be attributed to the fact that the interest on the external debt is always higher than the domestic interest rate; this matter differs between countries. Even if the developing countries are good with their exports, but their external debt interest is always higher, and therefore the US dollar appreciates more as developing countries have to bear its costs while borrowing for transactions

Implications of borrowings of the Government

These are briefly discussed below:

Higher debt interest installments: As getting builds, the public authority needs to pay more interest rate installments on the individuals who hold securities. This can prompt a more noteworthy level of tax revenue going to debt interest installments.

Higher interest rates: In certain conditions, higher acquiring can push up interest rates since business sectors are anxious about governments' capacity to reimburse, and they request higher security yields as a trade-off for apparent risk.

Higher taxes later on: On the off chance that the debt to GDP rises quickly, the public authority may have to pay off past commitments levels later on. It implies future budgets should increment taxes and additionally limit spending.

Defenseless against capital flight: On the off chance that an administration finances its deficiency by acquiring from abroad, at that point, there is potential for the economy to experience the ill effects of the capital trip later on.

Inflationary pressing factors: It is uncommon for Government acquiring to cause inflation. Yet, a few governments might be enticed to manage undeniable degrees of debt by printing more money. This increment in the money supply can make inflationary pressing factors increment.

CONCLUSION

This review has observed that Japan leads the nations among borrowing per capita at 236%, and Brunei is the lowest at two percent. Both developed and developing nations borrow from international credit markets based on their credibility to pay back the borrowed amount. The difference is that the poorer economies have to borrow in international currencies like the US dollar, and despite a good export of their products abroad, they still collect large external debts as compared to rich economies like the US. External debt is the main factor that destabilizes the capital flow into the country. The Government's implications of a high debt can be higher interest rates, inflation, and higher taxes.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Focus Economics. (2019). Economic Forecasts from the World's Leading Economists. Which countries have the highest public debt levels? <https://www.focus-economics.com/blog/countries-with-the-most-public-debt>.
- [2]. Gelos, R.G., Sahay, R., and Guido, S.(2004). Sovereign Borrowing by Developing Countries: What Determines Market Access? International Monetary Fund WP/04/221 IMF Working Paper Western Hemisphere Department.
- [3]. Holland, M. (2007). External debt in developing economies: assessment and policy issues. *Brazilian Journal of Political Economy*.
- [4]. Olson, M.J. (1996). Distinguished Lecture on Economics in Government Big Bills Left on the Sidewalk: Why Some Nations are Rich, and Others Poor. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 10(2), 3-24.
- [5]. Singer H.W. (1975). The Distribution of Gains between Investing and Borrowing Countries. In: The Strategy of International Development. Palgrave Macmillan, London. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-04228-9_3.

Annexure: Table – Full list of countries with public debt % of GDP.

Rank	Country	Public Debt % of GDP
1	Japan	236
2	Greece	175
3	Lebanon	153
4	Venezuela	152
5	Italy	131
6	Portugal	119
7	Singapore	116
8	Mozambique	114
9	United States	108
10	Belgium	100
11	France	98
12	Spain	96
13	Jordan	94
14	Cyprus	94

15	Bahrain	92
16	Jamaica	92
17	Puerto Rico	92
18	Belize	91
19	Egypt	88
20	United Kingdom	85
21	Yemen	84
22	Argentina	81
23	Brazil	79
24	Sri Lanka	77
25	Angola	74
26	Pakistan	74
27	Tunisia	73
28	El Salvador	73
29	Mongolia	72
30	Croatia	72
31	Austria	72
32	Uruguay	71
33	Hungary	70
34	Montenegro	70
35	Zambia	69
36	India	68
37	Slovenia	67
38	Ghana	66
39	Albania	66
40	Laos	65
41	Trinidad	65
42	Morocco	64
43	Ukraine	63

44	Ireland	61
45	Israel	60
46	Kenya	59
47	Costa Rica	59
48	Finland	59
49	Ethiopia	58
50	Vietnam	57
51	Germany	57
52	South Africa	57
53	Armenia	57
54	Kyrgyzstan	56
55	Serbia	55
56	Nicaragua	55
57	Tajikistan	55
58	Malaysia	52
59	Bolivia	52
60	Iraq	51
61	Qatar	51
62	Netherlands	50
63	Ecuador	49
64	Azerbaijan	49
65	Poland	49
66	Slovakia	48
67	Mexico	47
68	Oman	47
69	Cote d'Ivoire	47
70	Colombia	46
71	Belarus	46
72	Malta	44

73	Thailand	43
74	Uganda	43
75	Georgia	43
76	Macedonia	43
77	Dominican Republic	42
78	Tanzania	41
79	Philippines	41
80	Panama	40
81	Iran	40
82	Australia	40
83	Algeria	38
84	Korea	38
85	Bosnia	38
86	Romania	37
87	Lithuania	37
88	Latvia	37
89	Sweden	36
90	Iceland	35
91	Haiti	35
92	Cambodia	35
93	Cameroon	35
94	Denmark	35
95	Moldova	35
96	Myanmar	34
97	Norway	33
98	Bangladesh	33
99	Turkmenistan	33
100	Czech Republic	31
101	Taiwan	31

102	Turkey	30
103	Indonesia	30
104	New Zealand	28
105	Switzerland	28
106	Peru	27
107	Kuwait	26
108	Chile	26
109	Nigeria	26
110	Guatemala	26
111	Uzbekistan	24
112	Kazakhstan	24
113	Bulgaria	23
114	Saudi Arabia	22
115	Luxembourg	21
116	UAE	20
117	Paraguay	20
118	Kosovo	19
119	China	18
120	DRC	16
121	Botswana	15
122	Russia	13
123	Estonia	8
124	Brunei	2

(Source: Results from Focus Economics 2019)